

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS IN DICYCLOHEXANE DERIVATIVES. PART I.

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Ethyl 2-cyano-2-(2'-carbethoxycyclohexyl)-4-acetyl-butrate, obtained from ethyl 2-carb-ethoxycyclohexylcyanoacetate, on condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate, followed by addition of hydrocyanic acid, hydrolysis and esterification, furnishes (III, $R_1 = CO_2Et$; $R_2 = H$) which on cyclisation, methylation, hydrolysis and esterification yields (IV; $R = H$). The keto-ester on Reformatsky's reaction, followed by dehydration and hydrogenation yields (V).

In order to investigate the possibility of extending the method of synthesis of *trans-anti-trans*-perhydrophenanthrene (Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 85) for the preparation of *cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene*, the following pilot experiments have been performed.

The sodio derivative of ethyl 2-carbethoxycyclohexyl-1-cyanoacetate has been condensed with 4-chlorobutan-2-one in benzene solution according to the method of Banerjee (*ibid.*, 1940, 17, 453) to yield (I; $R = CN$). The substituted

4-acetyl butyrate is best hydrolysed with an excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid to the dibasic acid, which is esterified. The resulting keto-ester (I; $R = H$)

condenses with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the modified method of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452) to give diethyl 1-(2'-carbethoxycyclohexyl)-4-methyl-5-cyanopent-4-ene-1:5-dicarboxylate (II), which smoothly adds a molecule of hydrocyanic acid. The above succinic acid system on hydrolysis, followed by esterification, yields (III). The tetracarboxylic ester has been cyclised and methylated *in situ* to yield (IV), which can be distilled with slight decomposition. The above compound has been hydrolysed and esterified when (V) is obtained. The Reformatsky's reaction on the above keto-ester, followed by dehydration and hydrogenation, yields ethyl 2'-carbethoxy-3:4-dimethyl-4-carb-ethoxy-dicyclohexyl-2-acetate (VII).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Cyano-2-(2'-carbethoxycyclohexyl)-4-acetyl-butyrato (I ; R = CN).— Ethyl 2-carbethoxycyclohexylcyanoacetate (40 g.) was added to sodium dust (3.54 g.) covered with benzene (87 c.c.). After sometime sodium metal went into solution with the development of a red colour. The clear solution was cooled

in ice and then a solution of 4-chlorobutan-2-one (16 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.) was added when, however, heat was generated and the colour of the solution became light yellow. On standing for a few minutes a gelatinous mass was formed throughout the whole of the solution. The flask was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed for 30 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the resulting benzene layer was washed thrice with water, dried and distilled, b.p. 215°/5 mm., yield 20 g. (Found: C, 63.98; H, 8.12. $C_{18}H_{27}O_5N$ requires C, 64.09; H, 8.01 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was first obtained as a liquid, but solidified after a few months. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 115°. (Found: N, 14.51. $C_{19}H_{30}O_5N_4$ requires N, 14.21 per cent).

During the distillation decomposition set in, hence rapid distillation was essential. The condensation of the cyano-ester with methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one, according to the method of Du Feu, McQuillin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53) and Wilds and Shunk (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 471), gave a very poor yield of the condensation product.

6-(2'-Carbathoxycyclohexyl)-cyclohexane-1 : 3-dione (Ia).—The above substituted cyano-ester was refluxed with a mixture of sulphuric and acetic acids and water (5 : 7 : 7) for 35 hours. The crude acid fraction thus obtained was esterified and distilled. The boiling point was not constant, but the fraction boiling at 140-50°/5 mm. was the expected dione (II). (Found: C, 67.4; H, 8.3. $C_{15}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 67.7; H, 8.3 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(2'-Carbathoxycyclohexyl)-4-acetyl-butyrato (I; R=H).—The above substituted cyano-ester (I, 20 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (conc., 200 c.c.) for 36 hours. The precipitated oil was extracted thoroughly with ether which was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporation of the ether the residue was dried in a pump and esterified with alcohol (60 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 6 c.c.). The reaction mixture was diluted with ice-water and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was evaporated and the residue distilled, b.p. 148-55°/2 mm. (Found: C, 65.13; H, 8.88. $C_{17}H_{28}O_5$ requires C, 65.38; H, 8.97 per cent). The *semicarbazone* as well as the oximes of this keto-ester are liquids.

Diethyl 1-(2'-Carbathoxycyclohexyl)-4-methyl-5-cyano-pent-4-ene-1 : 5-dicarboxylate (II).—The above keto-ester (50 g.) together with ethyl cyanoacetate (19 c.c.), acetic acid (4 c.c.), ammonium acetate (4g.) and benzene (50 c.c.) was taken in a flask fitted with the apparatus recommended by Cope *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and refluxed for 12 hours. Afterwards another lot of ammonium acetate (3 g.) and acetic acid (3 c.c.) was added and the refluxing was continued for another 6 hours. The reaction mixture was taken in benzene and washed several times with water. The benzene solution was dried and distilled, b.p. 201-5°/1.5 mm., yield 34 g. (Found: C, 64.80; H, 8.0. $C_{22}H_{33}O_6N$ requires C, 64.86; H, 8.1 per cent).

Diethyl 1-(2'-Carbethoxycyclohexyl)-4-methyl-4-carbethoxy-pentane-1:5-dicarboxylate (II).—To the solution of the above unsaturated ester (34 g.) in alcohol (94.6 c.c.) and water (4.9 c.c.) was added slowly a solution of potassium cyanide (10.89 g.) in water (59.1 c.c.) when some heat was developed. This mixture of the reaction product and the reactants were cooled in ice-water for half an hour and then very slowly was added to it hydrochloric acid (conc., 14 c.c. and 9.3 c.c. of water) which was previously cooled for half an hour. After the addition of the acid, the mixture was cooled for further 20 minutes. Next it was poured into ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether. The ether was driven off and the residue was hydrolysed by refluxing it with concentrated hydrochloric acid (500 c.c.) for 48 hours. The clear solution was extracted twice with ether and then the mother-liquor was saturated with ammonium sulphate. The saturated solution was extracted seven times with ether. Both the ethereal solutions were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was driven off and the residue was esterified with alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (36 c.c.) by refluxing the mixture for one week. The ester was worked up in the above way and distilled, b.p. 205-10³/3 mm., yield 33 g. (Found : C, 63.23 ; H, 8.68. C₂₄H₄₀O₈ requires C, 63.16 ; H, 8.77 per cent).

2-(2'-Carbethoxycyclohexyl)-5 : 6-dimethyl-5-carbethoxycyclohexanone (V).—The tetra-ester (20 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (2 g.), benzene (50 c.c.) and alcohol (1 c.c.) on the water-bath for 3½ hours, when all the sodium metal reacted. The reaction mixture was decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid. The benzene layer was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried over calcium chloride. The benzene layer was driven off; the residual β -keto-ester, which furnished a positive ferric reaction, could not be distilled. The β -ketonic ester was dried under vacuum at 100° and treated with sodium dust (0.8 g.) and benzene (45 c.c.). The resulting sodio derivative was reacted with methyl iodide (2 moles) and refluxed for 7 hours. The methylated product in benzene was washed with water, dried and distilled with slight decomposition, b.p. 200-210°/4.5 mm., yield 10 g. It did not respond to ferric reaction. (Found : C, 66.1 ; H, 8.00. C₂₃H₃₆O₇ requires C, 65.09 ; H, 8.5 per cent). The high result of the analysis is due to a slight decomposition.

The above substituted β -keto ester (10 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19, 100 c.c.) for 40 hours. It was extracted with ether and esterified with alcohol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (10 c.c.), b.p. 185°/3.5 mm., yield 5.5 g. (Found : C, 68.46 ; H, 8.91. C₂₀H₃₂O₅ requires C, 68.18 ; H, 9.09 per cent).

Ethyl 2'-Carbethoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-4-carbethoxy-dicyclohexyl-2-acetate (VII).—A solution of the above keto-ester (5.5 g.) in thiophen-free benzene (40 c.c.) was heated with activated zinc (8 g.), a crystal of iodine and ethyl bromoacetate (4 c.c.) on the water-bath to drive away some benzene which took away the moisture of the flask. Next it was refluxed when a vigorous reaction set in. After half an hour, again zinc (5 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (2 c.c.) were added

and refluxing was continued for 2 hours. Another lot of zinc (5 g.) was added and heating continued for 3½ hours. The Reformatsky's reaction complex was decomposed by shaking with acetic acid (11 c.c.) and ethanol (10 c.c.). The reaction product was taken in ether and washed with cold alkali. The ether was driven off and the residue after drying under vacuum was taken in dry ether (20 c.c.) and pyridine (3 c.c.). The above solution, cooled in ice-water, was slowly treated with thionyl chloride (2 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight, decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid, washed with dilute bicarbonate solution and distilled, b.p. 200-5°/3.5 mm., yield 1.7 g. (Found : C, 68.1 ; H, 9.0. $C_{24}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 68.24 ; H, 9.0 per cent).

The above unsaturated ester in acetic acid solution was hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst. The absorption of hydrogen was very slow. After the absorption was complete, the catalyst was filtered and the solution was distilled, b.p. 205°/4.5 mm.

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